

COMPARISON OF E-SERVICE QUALITY ATTRIBUTES: ELECTRONIC RETAILING AND ELECTRONIC BANKING SECTORS

P.KRITHIKA

Research Scholar Department of Management, Vels Institute of Science, Technology & Advanced Studies, Chennai-TamilNadu. Email: anu.krithi4@gmail.com,

Dr.PSHALINI

Professor, HOD, MBA (LSCM) & Research Supervisor, Vels Institute of Science, Technology & Advanced Studies, Chennai-TamilNadu. Email: shalini.sms@velsuniv.ac.in

Abstract

The predominance of the web entails a better knowledge of electronic service quality attributes for today's world. To compare and analyze various service quality attributes in two sectors (1) electronic retailing (2) electronic banking. This article is focusing on the perception of all electronic service quality attributes. Further, it aims to know which is the most frequently used e-service attribute in these two sectors. We are using Comparison Of E-Service Quality Attributes in our study. The elements of every e-service quality measurement were all unique to one another. Because e-retailing (a hybrid of goods and services) and e-banking (pure service) are entirely two different sectors. The E-service quality is a crucial strategy for every e-marketer. It helps to expand the online companies and also dominates increasing the websites and offerings in a better way. The main element to get through in a savaged digital environment is to focus on the perception of e-service quality attributes in different e-platforms. A detailed paper addressed four service quality attributes that are (i) website design, (ii) customer service, security and (iv) fulfillment on both electronic retailing (associated with both goods and services) and electronic banking sectors (associated with service) have been studied. In our study we conclude website design is the primary attribute for e-retailing in contrast e-banking shows security and privacy attribute is considered as a primary attribute.

Keywords: E-Retailing, E-Banking, E-Service Quality attributes

INTRODUCTION

With the remarkable developments for Web, marketers embraced the advanced technology. They not only support brick and mortar tradition but also welcome the innovations mainly from the internet. The world of e-business has exploded over the decade. Business owners are turning their traditional stores into virtual experiences, and many new marketers use the web to sell their products and services. We broadly study about the two sectors one is online retailing the other is online banking. Retail online had acquired speed in the most recent decade. The web business area has been assessed to arrive at 14500 crores online purchasers by 2025 (Statista 2019-2025). With the continuous advanced drive in India, the purchasers choosing electronic banking is relied upon to significantly increase to show up at 260 crores by 2024 globally (Moneytransfers.com 2022). Colossal services like (e.g., Healthcare, food, travel industry, retailing, and so forth) possess online business. Online retailing and online banking services are, by and large, increasingly distributed step by step

online. After all, the standard of electronic service quality, the assistance of value customers in e-channels, is fundamental.

Comparison of E-Service Quality Attributes

The electronic service quality literature predominantly utilizes reflective measurements. Blut et al 2015. Adding to Blut et al 2016 attributes fifteen more attributes are added to these sixteen attributes which sums up to 31 attributes

Table 1: Categorizing Attributes - 31 Attributes to 4 Dimensions

WEBSITE DESIGN	FULFILMENT	SECURITY/ PRIVACY	CUSTOMER SERVICE	AUTHORS	PAPER NAME	NUMBER
efficiency, system availability, responsiveness, compensation, contact	Fulfillment	privacy	X	Parasuraman, A. Zeithaml, Valarie A. Malhotra, Arvind (2005)	E-S-QUAL a multiple-item scale for assessing electronic service quality	7 attributes
Website Information Quality, Website Org./Design/Navigation/Interaction Purchase Process Site Convenience/Ease of Use Shipment Tracking, Product Selection Merchandise Stock Availability, Price of Offerings	Timeliness of Delivery, Order Accuracy, Delivery Condition, Billing Accuracy, Merchandise Quality	X	Service Level 2. Return Policies	Holloway, Betsy BuggBeatty, Sharon E (2008).	Satisfiers and dissatisfiers in the online environment: A critical incident assessment	15 attributes
information quality, website aesthetics, purchase process, website convenience, product selection, merchandise availability, price offerings, website personalization, and system availability	time of delivery, order accuracy, and delivery condition	Security/privacy	service level and returns handling/return	Blut, Markus (2016)	E-Service Quality: Development of a Hierarchical Model	16 attributes
access, efficiency, ease of navigation, efficiency, flexibility, personalization, responsiveness, price knowledge assurance/trust,	reliability,	security/privacy	X	Zeithaml, Valarie A. Parasuraman, A. Malhotra, Arvind (2000)	A Conceptual Framework for Understanding e-Service Quality: Implications for Future Research and Managerial Practice - Marketing Science Institute	11 attributes
information quality, website aesthetics, purchase process, website convenience, product selection, merchandise availability, price offerings, website personalization, and system availability, Website navigation, ease of use, shipment tracking, interaction, efficiency, responsiveness, compensation, contact, price knowledge, access, assurance/trust	billing accuracy, merchandise quality, reliability, order accuracy, delivery condition, time of delivery	security and privacy	service level, return handling	IN THIS PAPER		31 attributes

Research Objectives

- Categorizing and figuring out electronic service quality attributes the one e-retailing and the other e-banking by using Comparison of E-Service Quality Attributes
- 31 attributes to 4 Dimensions – Website Design, Fulfillment, Privacy/security and customer service
- Reviewing about the acceptance percentage of comparison of e-service quality attributes on both sectors

LITERATURE REVIEW

Frequently Used Electronic Service Quality Attributes-Online Retailing and Online Banking

Blut et al. (2015) say the sixteen aspects of electronic service quality attributes comprised website design, customer service, fulfillment, security, and privacy. The **website design** aspects directly impacted nine attributes information quality, aesthetics, purchase process, website convenience, product selection, merchandise availability, price offerings, website personalization, and system availability. The **Fulfillment aspects** impacted on three attributes delivery timeliness, order accuracy, and delivery condition. The **Customer service aspects** impacted on two attributes service level and return handling/policies. Finally, **Security and privacy aspects** impacted on two attributes security and privacy.

E-service quality attributes applied for both sectors are given. Some are named below

- ✓ Website design.
- ✓ Fulfillment
- ✓ Customer service
- ✓ Security and Privacy

i). WEBSITE DESIGN

Website design is a foremost important feature for all e-channels. In the digital world of e-service website design is centered mainly because it's the customer's first impression about the product /service. The Perception of website design should meet subsequent sub-attributes

- ✓ quality of information provided on website should be effective and useful
- ✓ design of the website has to be visually pleasing and attractive
- ✓ Acquiring the product/service should not be troublesome
- ✓ The texts and labels of the website must be easy, clear and understandable
- ✓ Diversity of product/service ranges should be given
- ✓ The website shall provide low prices, offers, coupons, discounts, or free shipping
- ✓ Personalization of products/services expected as per customer needs
- ✓ Should be brisk reaction intermediate to purchaser's act and the site's response

ii). FULLFILLMENT

Customers request a product based on category, style, and color advertised on the site. Once they confirm the selected product, it gets dispatched. The verified product with shown price,

details will deliver within the time frame scheduled on the site. Fulfillment is the critical component of the electronic service quality aspects considering the product gets misplaced or not given correctly within the period the particular e-channel reputation will go in toss.

iii). CUSTOMER SERVICE

The primary point of customer service is servicing the customer related to complaints, queries, and requests of goods/services offered. This attribute is seen in all processes before, during, and after the purchasing process. Coming up next are the characteristic of customer service of e-service quality. (M. Blut et al 2016)

- ✓ Site must be helpful, responsive to customers during complaints/queries
- ✓ Site should offer worthwhile guarantee
- ✓ The website should handle the products return well
- ✓ Should provide phone number to reach the firm

iv). SECURITY AND PRIVACY

While purchasing the service/product, customers should feel secure to use their credit/debit cards. Online sites should make sure customer usage details are protected. (Holloway and Beatty 2008). Make feel customer more secure and safe while making the transaction on the website. After confirming the selected product/service on the site, customer pieces of information, visa/master card details should be protected and privatized. Customers are constantly concerned whether the site would ensure them against fraudulent after an exchange. The best vital feature to evaluate electronic -service quality in both e-channels is site privacy. The characteristic of security and privacy of e-service quality

- ✓ Site must protect the information about the usage of customer data while acquiring the product/service
- ✓ Customers should also sense the trustworthiness of the website

Table -2 Increase of Electronic Service Quality Attributes In E-Retailing

AUTHORS	WEBSITE DESIGN	FULFILMENT	CUSTOMER SERVICE	SECURITY /PRIVACY
Zeithaml, Valarie A.Parasuraman, A.Malhotra, Arvind(2000)	access, ease of navigation, efficiency, flexibility, reliability, personalization, site aesthetics, price knowledge, responsiveness, assurance	X	X	security/privacy
Wolfinger, Mary Gilly, Mary C.(2003)	website design, informativeness, personalization, ease of use, selection	fulfillment	customer service	privacy/security
Kim, Soyoung, Stoel, Leslie(2004)	website appearance, informational fit to task, entertainment, response time	X	X	trust, transaction capability
Jun,	reliable/prompt responses,	X	attentiveness	Security

MinjoonYang,Z hilin Kim,Dae Soo(2004)	access, ease of use,credibility			
Lee, Gwo GuangLin,Hsiu Fen(2005)	website design, reliability, responsiveness,personalization,t rust	X	X	X
Parasuraman, A.Zeithaml, Valarie A.Malhotra,Arvi nd(2005)	efficiency, fulfillment, system availability,responsiveness,com pensation,andcontact	fulfilment	X	Privacy
Kim, MinjeongKim,Ju ngHwan Lennon,SharronJ (.2006)	efficiency, browsing option, search engine, systemavailability, responsiveness, contact, companycontacts,personalizacao n,information	alternative ordermethod,fulf ilment	virtualcom munity	payment method,pr ivacy
Bai, BillyLaw,Rob Wen,Ivan(2008)	websitequality	X	X	X
Finn, AdamWang,Lum ing Frank,Tema(200 9)	appealing,easyread	Order	X	Privacy
Gounaris, Spiros Dimitriadis, Sergios Stathakopoulos, Vlasis(2010)	information, aesthetics, user friendliness	X	interaction	X
Finn, Adam (2011)	aesthetics, personalization, assurance, accessibility, reliability, information, responsiveness, site design, ease of use, navigation,	Returability (delivery)	customer support	Security
Subramanian, Nachiappan Gunasekaran, Angappa Yu, Jie Cheng, Jiang Ning, Kun(2013)	Reliability	X	X	X
Blut, Markus (2015)	information quality, web- site aesthetics, purchase process, website convenience, product selection, price offerings, website personalization, and system availability	time of delivery, order accuracy, and delivery condition	service level and returns handling / return	Security/p rivacy
yin ling chek et al (2016)	efficiency, system availability, responsiveness, contact, information quality	fulfillment	X	Privacy

Loureiro, Sandra M.C. Cavallero, Luisa Miranda, Francisco Javier (2018)	website content quality, information quality	X	X	X
Lopes, Evandro Luiz de Lamônica Freire, Otávio Bandeira Herrero Lopes, Eliane(2019)	Design	fulfillment	customer service	Privacy / security
Rita, P., Oliveira, T., & Farisa, A (2019)	information quality, website aesthetics, purchase process, website convenience, product selection, price offerings, website personalization, and system availability	time of delivery, order accuracy, and delivery condition	service level and returns handling/retur n	Security / privacy
Brusch, Ines Schwarz, Benjamin Schmitt, Rebecca (2019)	website, product portfolio	Delivery	support	Security / privacy
Nguyen, Thuan Thi Nhu(2020)	external incentives	X	customer service	Security / privacy

Table -3 Increase of Electronic Service Quality Attributes InE-Banking

AUTHORS	WEBSITEDESIGN	FULFILMENT	CUSTOMER SERVICE	SECURITY /PRIVACY
Jun,Minjoon Cai,Shaohan(2001)	reliability, responsiveness, competence, credibility,access,content, accuracy,easeofuse,aesthe tics	Timeliness	X	Security
Jayawardhena,Chanaka(2004)	Websiteinterface,reliabilit y,responsiveness,empathy and assurance	X	interaction	X
Mäenpää, KatariinaKale, Sudhir H.Kuusela, HannuMesiranta,Nina(2 008)	Convenience	X	X	Security
Yoon,Cheolho(2010)	easeofuse,design,informat ioncontent	X	customerserv icesupport	Security
Hu, Yi Chung Liao, Pen Che (2011)	efficiency, system availability, responsiveness, compensation, contact,	X	X	Privacy

	tangibility, reliability, continuous improvement personalization			
Ariff, Mohd Shoki Md Yun, Leong Ooi Zakuan, Norhayati Jusoh, Ahmad (2012)	efficiency, system availability, responsiveness, contact, assurance	Fulfillment	X	Privacy
Zavareh, Farnaz Beheshti Ariff, Mohd Shoki Md Jusoh, Ahmad Zakuan, Norhayati Bahari, Ahamad Zaidi Ashourian, Mohsen (2012)	efficient and reliable services, site aesthetics, responsiveness/contact, and ease of use	Fulfillment	X	Security
Aliyu, Alhaji Abubakar Rosmain, Tasmin Takala, Josu(2013)	Convenience	X	customer service delivery	Security
Ariff, Mohd Shoki Md Yun, Leong Ooi Zakuan, Norhayati Ismail, Khalid (2013)	assurance, efficiency-system availability, contact- responsiveness and website aesthetics	Fulfillment	X	Privacy
Ling, Goh Mei Fern, Yeo Sook Boon, Lim Kah Huat, Tan Seng (2016)	website design and content, convenience,	X	X	security and privacy
Asad, Mohsen Mazaheri Mohajerani, Najma Sadat Nourseresh, Mohammad (2016)	ease of use, responsiveness, contact, site aesthetic, efficient and reliable services	Fulfillment	X	Security
Chmielarz, Witold Zborowski, Marek (2018)	Visualization, Navigation, and user-friendliness, User- friendliness of (website, application), access	X	X	Security
Aboobucker, Ilmudeen Bao, Yukun(2018)	trust, web usability	X	X	security/privacy
George, Ajimon(2018)	efficiency, reliability, website attributes, responsiveness	Fulfilment	X	Privacy
Dianat, Iman Adeli, Pari Asgari Jafarabadi, Mohammad Karimi, Mohammad Ali (2019)	personalization, structure, navigation, layout, search and performance-website attributes	X	X	X
Li, Feng Lu, Hui Hou, Meiqian Cui, Kangle Darbandi, Mehdi (2021)	cloud services	X	X	banking system security

METHODOLOGY

Comparison of E-Service Quality Attributes is used to categorize the above all e-service quality attributes in both sectors. This comparison of all four aspects is not perfectly covered since it's a reflective measurement model. Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Malhotra (2005), say the frequently used measurement scale for electronic retailing is E-S Qual Measurement.

Figure 1

ATTRIBUTES	E-RETAILING	E-BANKING
Website Design	81	67
Fulfilment	13	6
Security/Privacy	21	15
Customer Service	10	2
Total	125	90
Not Acceptance Attributes	32	13
%Of Not Acceptance	20%	13%
%Of Acceptance	80%	87%
%Of Both Sector Acceptance	83%	

But this article recommends comparison of electronic service quality attribute a progressive build with 31 aspects. Further, these aspects divided into four dimensions, where these four main e-service quality aspects influence in general about the perception of e-service quality insights. **90 attributes** in e-banking, **125 attributes** in e-retailing are divided in four electronic service quality attributes. Number of attributes are counted and categorized in these 4 different main dimensions in both sectors. In above Figure 1 it has been summarized. The below graph describes the frequently used attributes in both sectors.

MAJOR FINDINGS

By comprising all the above e-service attributes from the above study, we are categorizing into four dimensions to get a better knowledge about the complete Concept of electronic service quality in two different sectors. Website Design attributes are used mostly in e-retailing sectors, whereas in e-banking sectors, it is security and privacy attribute. Some of the **not acceptance attributes** while applying this comparison of e-service quality attributes are found such as status, cancelable, shopping experience, reviews in e-retailing whereas in online banking clarity, risk, benefit etc. By using comparison of e-service quality attributes **83% of acceptance for this model can be clearly seen in both sectors**

MANAGERIAL IMPLICATION

Firstly, in electronic retailing and electronic banking sectors, all electronic service quality attributes are grouped into thirty-one attributes subsequently divided into four aspects this we can eventually identify the overall perception of e-service quality in both sectors. Secondly, it is beneficial for the researcher to focus on the least part of electronic service quality attributes in two individual sectors. We can also compare whether the least part of e-service quality attributes is the same or different in each channel. Lastly, this measurement can be used by e-marketers to permanently monitor the improvement initiatives of e-service quality attributes in the online channel.

LIMITATIONS

Rita et al 2019 say electronic service quality attributes differ in every sector so this comparison of electronic service quality may not apply to all aspects and dimensions. so, future research should analyze for any industry-specific like the airline industry, hotels, etc. or variety of product segments like clothing or electronics with this condition using the comparison of E-service Quality Attributes

REFERENCES

1. Aboobucker, I., & Bao, Y. (2018). What obstruct customer acceptance of internet banking? Security and privacy, risk, trust and website usability and the role of moderators. *Journal of High Technology Management Research*, 29(1), 109–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hitech.2018.04.010>
2. Aliyu, A. A., Rosmain, T., & Takala, J. (2014). Online Banking and Customer Service Delivery in Malaysia: Data Screening and Preliminary Findings. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 129, 562–570. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.03.714>
3. Ariff, M. S. M., Yun, L. O., Zakuan, N., & Ismail, K. (2013). The Impacts of Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty in Internet Banking. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 81, 469–473. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.06.462>
4. Ariff, M. S. M., Yun, L. O., Zakuan, N., & Jusoh, A. (2012). Examining Dimensions of Electronic Service Quality for Internet Banking Services. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 65 (ICIBSoS), 854–859. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.11.210>
5. Asad, M. M., Mohajerani, N. S., & Nourseresh, M. (2016). Prioritizing Factors Affecting Customer Satisfaction in the Internet Banking System Based on Cause-and-Effect Relationships. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 36(16), 210–219. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2212-5671\(16\)30032-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2212-5671(16)30032-6)

6. Bai, B., Law, R., & Wen, I. (2008). The impact of website quality on customer satisfaction and purchase intentions: Evidence from Chinese online visitors. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 27(3), 391–402. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2007.10.008>
7. Blut, M., Chowdhry, N., Mittal, V., & Brock, C. (2015). E-Service Quality: A Meta-Analytic Review. In *Journal of Retailing* (Vol. 91, Issue 4, pp. 679–700). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretai.2015.05.004>
8. Blut, M. (2016). E-Service Quality: Development of a Hierarchical Model. *Journal of Retailing*, 92(4), 500–517. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretai.2016.09.002>
9. Bruschi, I., Schwarz, B., & Schmitt, R. (2019). David versus Goliath - Service quality factors for niche providers in online retailing. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 50(January), 266–276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2019.05.008>
10. Chek, Y. L., & Ho, J. S. Y. (2016). Consumer Electronics E-retailing: Why the Alliance of Vendors' E-service Quality, Trust and Trustworthiness Matters. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 219, 804–811. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.05.083>
11. Chmielarz, W., & Zborowski, M. (2018). Analysis of e-Banking Websites' Quality with the Application of the TOPSIS Method - A Practical study. *Procedia Computer Science*, 126, 1964–1976. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2018.07.256>
12. Dabholkar, P. A., Shepherd, C. D., & Thorpe, D. I. (2000). A comprehensive framework for service quality: An investigation of critical conceptual and measurement issues through a longitudinal study. *Journal of Retailing*, 76(2), 139–173. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4359\(00\)00029-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4359(00)00029-4)
13. Dianat, I., Adeli, P., Asgari Jafarabadi, M., & Karimi, M. A. (2019). User-centred web design, usability and user satisfaction: The case of online banking websites in Iran. *Applied Ergonomics*, 81(November 2018), 102892. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apergo.2019.102892>
14. Finn, A. (2011). Investigating the non-linear effects of e-service quality dimensions on customer satisfaction. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 18(1), 27–37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2010.09.002>
15. Finn, A., Wang, L., & Frank, T. (2009). Attribute Perceptions, Customer Satisfaction and Intention to Recommend E-Services. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 23(3), 209–220. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intmar.2009.04.006>
16. George, A. (2018). Perceptions of Internet banking users— a structural equation modelling (SEM) approach. *IIMB Management Review*, 30(4), 357–368. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iimb.2018.05.007>
17. Gounaris, S., Dimitriadis, S., & Stathakopoulos, V. (2010). An examination of the effect of service quality and satisfaction on customers' behavioral intentions in e-shopping. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 24(2), 142–156. <https://doi.org/10.1108/08876041011031118>
18. Hu, Y. C., & Liao, P. C. (2011). Finding critical criteria of evaluating electronic service quality of Internet banking using fuzzy multiple-criteria decision making. *Applied Soft Computing Journal*, 11(4), 3764–3770. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2011.02.008>
19. Holloway, B. B., & Beatty, S. E. (2008). Satisfiers and dissatisfiers in the online environment: A critical incident assessment. *Journal of Service Research*, 10(4), 347–364. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094670508314266>
20. Jayawardhena, C. (2004). Measurement of Service Quality in Internet Banking: The Development of an Instrument. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 20(1–2), 185–207. <https://doi.org/10.1362/026725704773041177>
21. Jun, M., & Cai, S. (2001). The key determinants of Internet banking service quality: A content analysis. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 19(7), 276–291. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02652320110409825>
22. Jun, M., Yang, Z., & Kim, D. S. (2004). Customers' perceptions of online retailing service quality and their satisfaction. *International Journal of Quality and Reliability Management*, 21(8), 817–840. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02656710410551728>
23. Kim, S., & Stoel, L. (2004). Apparel retailers: Website quality dimensions and satisfaction. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 11(2), 109–117. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0969-6989\(03\)00010-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0969-6989(03)00010-9)
24. Kim, M., Kim, J. H., & Lennon, S. J. (2006). Online service attributes available on apparel retail websites: An E-S-QUAL approach. *Managing Service Quality*, 16(1), 51–77. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09604520610639964>
25. Lee, G. G., & Lin, H. F. (2005). Customer perceptions of e-service quality in online shopping. *International Journal of Retail and Distribution Management*, 33(2), 161–176. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09590550510581485>

26. Li, F., Lu, H., Hou, M., Cui, K., & Darbandi, M. (2021). Customer satisfaction with bankservices:Theroleofcloudservices,security,e-learningandservicequality. *TechnologyinSociety*, 64(December 2020), 101487. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2020.101487>
27. Ling, G. M., Fern, Y. S., Boon, L. K., & Huat, T. S. (2016). Understanding CustomerSatisfaction ofInternet Banking: A Case Study In Malacca. *Procedia Economics andFinance*, 37(16), 80–85.[https://doi.org/10.1016/s2212-5671\(16\)30096-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2212-5671(16)30096-x)
28. Lopes,E.L.,deLamônicaFreire,O.B.,&HerreroLopes,E.(2019).Competingscalesformeasuring perceived quality in the electronic retail industry: A comparison between E-S-QualandE-TailQ.*ElectronicCommerceResearchandApplications*,34(December2018),100824.<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.el erap.2019.100824>
29. Loureiro, S. M. C., Cavallero, L., & Miranda, F. J. (2018). Fashion brands on retailwebsites: Customer performance expectancy and e-word-of-mouth. *Journal of Retailingand Consumer Services*, 41(November 2017), 131–141.<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2017.12.005>
30. Mäenpää, K., Kale, S. H., Kuusela, H., & Mesiranta, N. (2008). Consumer perceptions ofInternet banking in Finland: The moderating role of familiarity. *Journal of Retailing andConsumer Services*, 15(4), 266–276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2007.05.007>
31. Moneytransfers.com2022-<https://moneytransfers.com/news/content/online-banking-statistics>
32. Nguyen, T. T. N. (2020). Developing and validating five-construct model of customersatisfactioninbeautyandcosmeticE-commerce.*Heliyon*,6(9),e04887.<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04887>
33. Parasuraman,A.,Zeithaml,V.A.,&Malhotra,A.(2005).E-S-QUALAmultiple-itemscaleforassessingelectronic servicequality.*JournalofServiceResearch*,7(3),213–233.<https://doi.org/10.1177/1094670504271156>
34. Rita, P., Oliveira, T., & Farisa, A. (2019). The impact of e-service quality and customersatisfactiononcustomerbehaviorinonlineshopping.*Heliyon*,5(10),e02690.<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e02690>
35. Statista.com<https://www.statista.com/statistics/255359/online-retail-sales-in-india/>
36. Subramanian, N., Gunasekaran,A., Yu, J., Cheng, J., & Ning, K. (2014). Customersatisfaction and competitiveness in the Chinese E-retailing: Structural equation modeling(SEM) approach to identify the role of quality factors. *Expert Systems with Applications*,41(1), 69–80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2013.07.012>
37. Wolfinger,M.,&Gilly,M.C.(2003).eTailQ:Dimensionalizing,measuringandpredictingetailquality.*Journalof Retailing*,79(3),183–198.[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4359\(03\)00034-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4359(03)00034-4)
38. Yoon, C. (2010). Antecedents of customer satisfaction with online banking in China: Theeffectsofexperience.*ComputersinHumanBehavior*,26(6),1296–1304.<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2010.04.001>
39. Zavareh, F. B., Ariff, M. S. M., Jusoh, A., Zakuan, N., Bahari, A. Z., & Ashourian, M.(2012). E-Service Quality Dimensions and Their Effects on E-Customer Satisfaction inInternet BankingServices.*Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 40, 441–445.<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.03.213>
40. Zeithaml,V. A., Parasuraman, A., & Malhotra, A. (2000). AConceptual Framework forUnderstanding e-Service Quality: Implications for Future Research and ManagerialPractice- Marketing ScienceInstitute.*Marketing ScienceInstitute*.